

Food Processing Industry in India : Problems and Prospects

Paper Id : 20789 Submission Date : 2025-08-05 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-21 Publication Date : 2025-08-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18060499

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/shinkhlala.php#8>

Anshu Veenapani

Research Scholar
Commerce Department
T.M.B.U.
Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

Abstract

The majority of people dwelling in rural areas of India draw their sustenance from agriculture and allied sectors. But the growth and balanced development of other sectors, such as industry and services is also necessary to sustain the growth of Indian economy in an inclusive manner.

Traditionally, Food processing has been an important part of the rural and semi-urban economy with pickles, jams, chutneys, papads being made by women at the household level. A progressive and vibrant food processing industry fetches more remunerative price for farmers and reduces wastes. Food processing encompasses products of fruits and vegetables, dairy, meat, poultry, fishery, grains, alcoholic drinks, aerated water and soft drink. It involves all types of value addition to agricultural or horticultural produces and includes processes such as grading, sorting and packaging which enhance self life of food products. The food processing sector comprises of two segments, viz. primary processed food and vegetables, milk, flour, rice, spices etc. value added segment includes processed fruits and vegetables, juice, jam, jelly etc.

Food processing industry in India is seen as a potential source for driving rural economy, as it brings synergy between industry and agriculture. A developed food producing industry would lead to increase in farm gate prices, translating into increased rural incomes. The paper intends to explain the purpose and problems of food processing industry in India and tries to find out solutions and policy options.

Keywords

Sustenance, Synergy, Allied, Aerated, Addition, Horticulture etc.

Introduction

The majority of people living in rural areas draw their livelihood from agriculture and allied sectors. The growth and balanced development of other sectors such as industry and services is also necessary to sustain the growth of Indian economy in an inclusive manner. The government of India is serving to improve the economic and social condition of rural population and non-farm sector through host of measures including creation of productive employment opportunities based on optimal use of local raw materials and skills.

Traditionally, Food processing has been an important part of the rural and semi-urban economy, with pickles, jams, chutneys, papads being made by women at the household level. As an industry, the food processing sector is yet to realize its potential. A progressing and vibrant food processing industry fetches more remunerative price for farmers and reduces waste. Availability of raw materials for food processing industry is a major strength of India. The demand for processed foods has increased due to growing middle and upper middle income groups, increasing health consciousness, growing number of working women and time constraint, convenience and need for hygienic food. Malls and departmental stores in metros, medium and small towns are providing forward linkages.

Food processing encompasses products of fruits and vegetables, dairy, meat, poultry, fishery, grains, alcoholic drinks, aerated water and soft drink. It involves all types of value addition to agricultural or horticultural produce and includes processes such as grading, sorting and packaging which enhance shelf life of food products. The Food processing sector comprises of two segments, viz. primary processed food and value added food. Primary segment comprises of packaged fruits and vegetables, milk, flour, rice, spices etc. Value added segment includes processed fruits and vegetables, juices, jam and jelly etc.

Food processing industry in India is seen as a potential source for driving rural economy, as it brings synergy between industry and agriculture. A developed food processing industry could lead to increase in farm gate prices, translating into increased rural incomes.

Objective of study

Government of India is setting up of food parks in different parts of the country so that small and medium entrepreneurs find access to capital-intensive facilities, such as cold storage, ware house, quality control laboratories, effluent treatment plants etc. Development of such facilities is expected to make the food processing units in the food parks cost competitive besides improving their market accessibility. Government is also operating schemes for the promotion of total quality management including ISO, hazard analysis, good manufacturing practices, good hygienic practices etc. with the following objectives :

1. To motivate the food processing industries for adoption of food safety and quality assurance mechanism,
2. To prepare them to face the global competition in the post-WTO era,
3. To enable adherence to a stringent quality in hygiene norms,
4. To enhance product acceptance by overseas buyers,

5. To keep Indian food safety industry technologically abreast of international best practices,
6. In addition, Government is also working towards the promotion of bar coding which is a compulsory requirement in the global market.

The subjects looked after by Ministry of Food processing industry are as under :

1. Fruits and vegetables processing industry
2. Food grain milling industry
3. Dairy products
4. Processing of poultry and eggs, meat and meat products
5. Fish Processing

Bread, oilseeds, meals, breakfast foods, biscuits, confectionery (including cocoa processing and chocolate), malt extract, protein isolate, high protein food, weaning food and extrude (other ready to eat food products)

1. Beer, including non-alcoholic bear
2. Alcoholic drinks from non-molasses base
3. Aerated waters/soft drinks and other processed foods
4. Specialized packaging for food processing industries
5. Technical assistance and advice to food processing industry
6. In the era of economic liberalization where the private, public and cooperative sectors are to play their rightful roles in the development of food processing sector, the ministry of FPI acts as a catalyst for bringing in greater investment into this sector, guiding and helping the industry in a proper direction, encouraging exports and creating a conducive environment for the healthy growth of the food processing industry.

Review of Literature

Many scholars have done a lot of work on rural industries especially food processing. S.S.P. Sharma (2003) has written a paper on Development Programmes, Environment and Rural Poverty in India'. Thamarajakshi, R. (1999) has also written an article on 'Agriculture and Economy'. Radhakrishna, R. (2002) has published an article on 'Food and Nutrition Security.' Konar D.N. (1997) has written a paper on 'Trend of Indian Agriculture in the Post – independence period.' The article of V.S. Vyas (2001) on 'Agriculture : Second Round of Economic Reforms' throws light on rural industrialisation. Rao C.H. Hanumantha and Ashok Gulati (1994) have dwelt on 'Indian agriculture : Emerging Perspectives and policy Issues'. The books of N. Mani (2019), E. Satyamurthy (2020) and A. Vaidyanathan (2014) are very important in this regard.

Methodology

The data have been procured from secondary sources and conclusions have been drawn based on empirical analysis.

Result and Discussion

Constraints/Problems of Food Processing Industry :

While the food processing sector offers several opportunities, it faces various constraints:

Lack of Robust Policy Mechanism

The absence of a well spelt out policy at the level of Central and State Governments, addressing the sectoral needs of the industry, is one of the major factors impeding the growth of this sector. Despite the Central Government's initiative in developing a vision document assessing the needs of the food processing industry, food processing policies are not being followed with definite action plan at the level of states.

Marketing Problems

States generally discourage direct marketing arrangement between farmers and processors. The processors are required to obtain license from the respective state governments, as well as pay market fees without using mandi infrastructure. States have not clearly outlined policies on contract farming/direct farming.

Essential Commodities Act

The essential Commodities Act, 1955 was put in place after Independence to control production, Supply and distribution of essential agricultural commodities and to ensure availability of food products. In the current context of liberalization, controlling the movement of products – by licensing of dealers, limits on stocks and controls on movements hampers the growth of the agricultural sector and promotion of food processing industries.

Burden of Taxes

Incidence of taxes on processed agricultural products not only acts as a disincentive for investment in the sector, but also affects the competitiveness of food products in the country. Though primary agricultural commodities (including fruits and vegetables) are mostly exempted from GST, processed food commodities are subject to different rates of GST. In most of the states, low value added products are exempted from goods and services tax (GST). However, certain high value added food products like biscuits, confectionery, snack items are levied GST at the rate of 12 percent or more.

Non-tariff barriers

These barriers include detailed food labelling requirements for packaged goods and compulsory detention and laboratory testing of samples of each imported item which boost overhead costs.

Some other reasons holding back the growth of food processing industry are as under

1. Restrictions imposed by State Government/Union territories on storage of food and agricultural produce.
2. Inadequate infrastructure along the value chain

3. Lack of infrastructure for post – harvest handling and storage
4. Absence of cold chain facilities
5. Fragmented supply chain of food products
6. Absence of institutional mechanism to facilitate linkage between the farmer and the processor markets.
7. Absence of a reliable database of food processing industry which affects the planning process adversely.
8. Considering the high risk involved in food processing, a supportive insurance policy is critical to the growth of the sector, which does not exist currently.
9. There is a need to involve industry for product development, setting up of food development centres/incubation centres on a regional basis in various prominent agro-climatic zones.
10. The current Indian crop production system largely continues to be traditional and subsistence agriculture. As a result, crop varieties being grown are not in tune with market and processing requirements.
11. The Vast Indian market is broken up into smaller level/regional markets and the high cost involved in transporting agricultural commodities and processed food from one part of the country to another involves a considerable drag on the efficiency of the food processing sector. Reducing the transaction cost would help in the reduction of ultimate price paid by the consumer, improving the competitiveness of Indian agriculture.

Solutions and Policy options

The self life of foodgrains is over 3 years or even more as against fruits and vegetables which have a self life varying between 01 week and 03 months. Hence, strategies for diversified agriculture should involve a separate road map for value addition in fruits and vegetable sector. Creation of essential infrastructure for preservation, cold storage, refrigerated transportation, rapid transit, grading, processing, packaging and quality control should be the key areas for such a strategy.

Solutions and policy options for the orderly growth of food processing industry can be prioritized as under

1. Provision of adequate infrastructural facilities;
2. Comprehensive national and state level policies regarding food processing sector;
3. Convergence in central and state policies;
4. Implementation of food safety laws;
5. Improvement in the availability of trained manpower;
6. Removal of constraints in raw material production, both quantity and variety;
7. Improvement in access to credit;
8. Development of cost effective packaging technologies;
9. Increased focus on organic food;
10. Export Promotion values;
11. Technology transfer and development.

Conclusion

There is tremendous scope for improving efficiency of the Indian agriculture in general and food processing in particular by removing interstate barriers which lead to high transaction costs. The case in print for consideration is the unification of European market.

Various regions in the country have immense potential for organic farming and thereby creating a niche market for organic food. This has to be systematically promoted through appropriate policy interventions and liberal support for achieving certification, capacity building, packaging and market linkages.

References

1. Ahluwalia, M.S. (1978) : 'Rural Poverty and Agricultural Performance in India', *Journal of Development studies*, vol. (3) April.
2. Konar, D. N. (1997) : 'Trend of Indian Agriculture in the Post-Independence Period', *Artha Beekha*, vol. 6, No.2, December.
3. N. Mani (2019) : *Rural Development, Poverty Eradication and Employment Generation in India*, New Century Publications, Ansari Road, New Delhi.
4. Satyanarayan G. and H.S. Madhusudan (2012) : *Rural Development and Poverty Alleviation in India*, New Century Publication, New Delhi.
5. Vaidyanathan, A. (2000) : 'Indian Agricultural Policy', *Economic & Political Weekly*, May 16.
6. <https://www.pib.gov.in/newsite/erecontent.aspx?relid=39268>